

“ISOLATION OF PLASTIC DEGRADING BACTERIA BY VARIOUS SOURCES.”

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ABSTRACT

Plastic wastes accumulation in the environment are posing an ever increasing ecological threat. The microorganisms having plastic degrading ability can be exploited for bioremediation of plastic waste accumulated site .To isolate the plastic degrading bacteria from plastic dumped soil. This study has covered the major concerns about the natural and synthetic polymers, their types, uses and degradability also it has looked at the disposal methods and the standards used in assessing polymer degradation. Another area examined has been the biodegradation of plastics by the liquid culture method. It is clear that most recalcitrant polymers can be degraded to some extent in the appropriate environment at the right concentration. The present study deals with the isolation, identification and degradative ability of plastic degrading microorganisms from soil.

Pre-weighed discs of 1-cm diameter prepared from polythene bags were aseptically transferred to the conical flask containing 50 ml of culture broth medium, inoculated with different bacterial species. Control was maintained with plastic discs in the microbe-free medium. Different flasks were maintained for each treatment and left in a shaker. After one month of shaking, the plastic discs were collected, washed thoroughly using distilled water,

shade-dried and then weighed for final weight. From the data collected, weight loss of the plastics was calculated and three plastic degrading bacteria were obtained.

The isolated microbes were native to the site of polyethylene disposal and shown some degradability in natural conditions, yet they also exhibited biodegradation in laboratory conditions on synthetic media.

Keywords: Polyethylene, Soil, Minimal Agar, Microorganism's.

Introduction:

Plastics are defined as the polymers (solid materials) which on heating become mobile and can be cast into moulds. They are non metallic mouldable compounds and the materials that are made from them can be pushed into any desired shape and sizes. Commonly plastics are used in many purposes including packaging, disposable diaper backing, agricultural films and fishing nets. Plastics and their use has become a part in all sectors of economy. Infrastructure such as agriculture, telecommunication, building and construction, consumer goods, packaging, health and medical are all high growth areas that ensures present demand for plastics. Plastic is the mother industry to hundreds of components and products that are manufactured and used in our daily life like automobiles parts, electrical goods, plastic furniture, defence materials, agriculture pipes, packages and sanitary wares, pipes and fittings, tiles and flooring, artificial leathers, bottles and jars, PVC shoes and sleepers hundreds of household items. Plastics are used in packaging of products such as food, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, detergents and chemicals. Approximately 30% of plastics are used worldwide for packaging applications and the most widely used plastics used for packaging are polyethylene (LDPE, MDPE, HDPE, LLDPE), polypropylene (PP), polystyrene (PS), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polyurethane (PUR), polybutylene terephthalate (PBT), nylons. At present the industry is split into organized and unorganized sectors. The organized sector produce quality products whereas unorganized sector is not capable of producing quality products, it produces low quality, cheap products through excessive use of plastic scrap.

Plastic wastes accumulating in the environment are posing an ever increasing ecological threat. Plastics that are biodegradable can be considered environment friendly, they have an increasing range of potential application and are driven by the growing use of plastics in packaging. In this study, the biodegradation of polythene bag was analysed 1 month of incubation in liquid culture method. Microbial counts in the degrading materials were recorded up to 0.0278×10^9 per gram for total heterotrophic bacteria. The microbial species found associated with the degrading materials were identified as two Gram positive and five Gram negative bacteria. The microbial species associated with the polythene materials were identified as *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Pseudomonas*. The efficacy of microbes in the degradation of plastics were analysed in liquid (shaker) culture method, among the bacteria

Bacillus cereus degrades plastic more in 1 month (30% weight loss/month) period compared to others and lowest degradation rate was observed in case of *Bacillus subtilis* (20% weight loss/month). This work reveals that *Bacillus subtilis* spores greater potential to degrade plastics when compared with other bacteria.

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MICROORGANISMS INVOLVED IN DEGRADATION OF PLASTIC:

The microbial species are associated with the degrading materials. Microbial degradation of plastics is caused by certain enzymatic activities that lead to a chain cleavage of the polymer into oligomers and monomers. These water soluble enzymatically cleaved products are further absorbed by the microbial cells where they are metabolized. Aerobic metabolism results in carbon dioxide and water, and anaerobic metabolism results in the production of carbon dioxide, water and methane and are called end products, respectively. The degradation leads to breaking down of polymers to monomers creating an ease of accumulation by the microbial cells for further degradation. Microorganisms can degrade plastic over 90 genera, from bacteria and fungi, among them; *Bacillus species*, *Pseudomonas species*. Plastic degradation by microbes due to the activity of certain enzymes that cause cleavage of the polymer chains into monomers and oligomers. Plastic that has been enzymatically broken down further absorbed by the microbial cells to be metabolized. Aerobic metabolism produces carbon dioxide and water. Instead of anaerobic metabolism produces carbon dioxide, water, and methane as end products. The purpose of this study was to isolate microorganism from dumped soil area and screening of the potential plastic degrading microorganisms and identifying the high potential microorganism that degrade the plastics.

Materials and Methods:

1) Sample collection

Plastic bags and soil sample was collected from the dumped yard soil.

2) Isolation

a) Serial dilution:

After the collection of plastic sample, these were taken and 1gm of this sample was cut into pieces and added to 9 ml of sterile water to make 1:10 dilution, adding 1ml of the 1:10 dilution of 9ml of sterile water makes a 1:100 dilution and so on.

b) Total heterotrophic count:

C.F.U. /g= Number of colonies/ inoculum size (ml) X dilution factor

3) Identification

Identification of the isolates were performed according to their morphological, cultural and biochemical characteristics by following of Systematic Bacteriology. All the isolates were subjected to Gram staining and specific biochemical tests.

1] MORPHOLOGICAL GRAM STAINING METHOD:

A clean grease free slide was taken and a smear of the bacterial culture was made on it with a sterile loop. The smear was air-dried and then heat fixed. Then it was subjected to the following staining reagents:

3.1] CATALASE TEST: The catalase test was performed to detect the presence of catalase enzyme by inoculating a loopful of culture into tubes containing 3% of hydrogen peroxide solution. Positive test was indicated by formation of effervescence or appearance of bubbles, due to the breaking down of hydrogen peroxide to O₂ and H₂O.

3.2] OXIDASE TEST: The oxidase test was done with the help of commercially available disc coated with a dye N-tetraethyl paraphenylene diamine dihydrochloride, to detect cytochrome 'c' oxidase which is responsible for the oxidation of the dye. Rubbing a small quantity of bacterial culture by means of a sterile toothpick on the disc causes formation of purple colour within 10-30 sec indicating positive reaction whereas no colour change indicates a negative reaction.

3.3] MANNITOL TEST: This experiment is generally performed to determine whether the bacteria is capable of fermenting mannitol sugar or not. Whenever organisms ferment mannitol agar, the pH of media becomes acidic due to production of acids. The fermentation of the media form red to yellow which shows positive test result.

3.4] MOTILITY TEST: The motility test was done to determine the motility of the organism. Bacterial cultures were stabbed into the motility test medium and were incubated at 37 C for 48 hrs. Turbidity and observation of growth besides the stab line indicated a positive reaction whereas clear visibility with growth indicated a negative reaction.

3.5] NITRATE REDUCTION TEST: This test was done to test if microorganisms are able to convert nitrate to nitrite or not by adding 1-2 drops of sulphanilic acid and 1-2 drops of N,

N-Dimethyl-Napthylanine reagent to the kitmedium. Immediate development of pinkish red colour there on addition of reagent indicates positive reaction. Negative reaction could be observed if there is no change in the colour.

3.6] CITRATE UTILISATION TEST: This test determines the ability of bacteria to convert citrate into oxaloacetate. Citrate is the only carbon source available to the bacteria in this media. If bacteria cannot use citrate, it will not grow. Positive result is seen if the bacteria grows and the media turns into bright blue colour as a result of an increase in the pH of the media.

3.7] GAS PRODUCTION FROM GLUCOSE: Gas production from glucose was assessed by inoculating the isolated strains in MRS broth containing glucose containing Durham tube in inverted condition and incubated at 37°C for 48- 72 hrs. The upward movement of inverted Durham tube indicates positive reaction (gas production).

4) Screening of Plastics in Laboratory Condition:

Determination of Weight Loss:

1. Determination:

Pre-weighed discs of 1-cm diameter prepared from polythene bags were aseptically transferred to the conical flask containing 50 ml of culture broth medium, inoculated with different bacterial species. Control was maintained with plastic discs in the microbe-free medium. Different flasks were maintained for each treatment and left in a shaker. After one month of shaking, the plastic discs were collected, washed thoroughly using distilled water, shade-dried and then weighed for final weight. From the data collected, weight loss of the plastics was calculated.

2. Determination:

Pre-weighed discs of 1-cm diameter prepared from polythene bags were aseptically transferred on Minimal agar plate and Nutrient agar plate .Incubate the plates at 37 c for several days. Observe the bacterial growth on surrounding the 1-cm diameter plastic .Then proceeds to motility, gram staining, and biochemical characters of growth colony. After the plastic discs are taken and weight measure.

$$\text{Weight loss determination} = \frac{\text{initial weight} - \text{final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

From the different calculated value of polyethylene degradation the percentage of degradation was determined.

Results and Discussion:

Isolation of plastic degrading bacteria. The three isolates were obtained. These isolates were designated as PDB₁, PDB₂, PDB₃.

Table 1 : Cultural and morphological characterization of the isolates:

Isolate	Size	Shape	Colour	Margin	Gram staining	Motility
PDB ₁	1.5mm	Circular	Greenish	Entire	Gram negative	Motile
PDB ₂	1mm	Circular	White	Entire	Gram positive	Motile
PDB ₃	1mm	Circular	White	Entire	Gram positive	Motile

Table 2 : Results of biochemical characterization of Isolates:

Isolates	Oxidase test	Catalase	Urease production	Indole test
PDB ₁	-	+	-	+
PDB ₂	+	+	-	+
PDB ₃	+	+	-	+

Isolates	Methyl red	Hydrolase test	Citrate	Glucose	Mannitol
PDB ₁	-	-	-	+	+
PDB ₂	+	+	+	+	+
PDB ₃	+	+	+	+	+

Notations :

+ : Indicates positive test

- : Indicates negative test

Table 3 : Results of screening of plastic degrading ability:

ISOLATES	Initial weight of plastic	Final weight of plastic	Difference in plastic weight	Weight loss of plastic in %
PDB ₁	0.1	0.08	0.02	2%
PDB ₂	0.1	0.06	0.04	4%
PDB ₃	0.1	0.05	0.05	5%

PDB₁: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

PDB₂: *Bacillus cereus*.

PDB₃: *Bacillus subtilis*.

Photograph 1: Photographs Showing Plastic Degrading Growth Was Observed On Minimal Agar Plates.

Summary and Conclusions:

The bacteria were identified to be *Bacillus Subtilis*, *Bacillus cereus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *Bacillus cereus* degrades plastic more than that of other bacteria. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* has less capacity to degrade plastic as compared to other bacteria. The isolated microbes were native to the site of polyethylene disposal and shown some degradability in natural conditions, yet they also exhibited biodegradation in laboratory conditions on synthetic media.

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